

Effect of *Azolla mexicana* and NH₄NO₃ treatments on dry matter production and N uptake of rice, Göttingen, West Germany.^a

Treatment	Straw		Grains		Total		Increase ^b (%)					
	DM (g/pot)	N (mg/pot)	DM (g/pot)	N (mg/pot)	DM (g/pot)	N (mg/pot)	1			2		3
							DM (g/pot)	N (mg/pot)	DM (g/pot)	N (mg/pot)	DM (g/pot)	N (mg/pot)
Azolla (t/ha)												
A0	2.16	7.61	1.58	12.91	3.74	20.52	—	—	—	—	—	—
A10	2.70	11.48	1.66	14.95	4.36	26.42	17	29	17	29	30	30
A20	2.92	14.28	1.99	17.56	4.91	31.84	31	55	13	21	28	28
A30	3.47	16.35	2.21	20.35	5.68	36.69	52	79	16	15	27	27
A40	4.02	20.45	2.72	25.46	6.75	45.91	80	124	12	25	32	32
A50	5.55	26.12	3.35	33.56	8.90	59.68	138	191	32	30	39	39
A60	5.95	29.14	4.32	42.70	10.27	71.84	175	250	15	20	43	43
A70	5.00	25.09	3.14	36.01	8.14	61.10	118	198	-21	-15	29	29
CD (5%)	.82	4.82	.54	6.03	1.15	9.31						
N (kg/ha)												
N0	2.16	7.61	1.58	12.91	3.74	20.52	—	—	—	—	—	—
N30	2.81	10.40	1.79	15.21	4.60	25.61	23	25	23	25	26	26
N60	3.24	12.11	2.48	20.43	5.71	32.55	53	56	24	27	30	30
N90	4.83	19.68	2.72	23.23	1.55	42.91	101	109	32	32	37	37
N120	4.98	16.76	3.80	31.58	8.18	48.34	135	136	16	13	35	35
N150	5.37	20.61	3.92	36.59	9.28	57.20	148	179	6	18	37	37
N180	6.03	24.85	4.56	41.26	10.59	66.12	183	222	14	16	38	38
N210	5.74	23.58	4.66	42.33	10.40	65.92	178	221	-2	—	32	32
CD (5%)	0.67	3.50	0.65	5.14	1.01	6.10						

^a Each value is a mean of 4 replications. ^b DM = dry matter production, N = nitrogen uptake. 1 = increase over control, 2 = increase over corresponding control, 3 = N uptake of the applied N (A10 = N30).

andy and had low plant status. Before the 2-kg pots were filled with sieved soil, the soil was mixed with monocalcium-phosphate (MCP) at 90 kg P/ha. Four days after transplanting, 80 kg K/ha as K₂SO₄ and 40 kg Mg/ha as MgSO₄ were applied. *Azolla mexicana* (6/62) from Brazil was grown in water tubs and mixed into the soil 1 wk before transplanting at 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, and 70 t fresh weight/ha. In parallel

treatments, NH₄NO₃ was applied at 30, 60, 90, 120, 180, and 210 kg N/ha, 1 wk after transplanting. Three 50-d-old IR28 seedlings were transplanted in each pot and ripened to maturity. Pots remained submerged throughout the experiment. Grain and straw yield are in the table.

Maximum yield was achieved with 60 t azolla/ha and 180 kg N/ha as NH₄NO₃ (see table). Yields at 10 t azolla/ha and NH₄NO₃ at 30 kg N/ha

were generally comparable. Highest N concentrations in straw and grain were in azolla treatments because there was more growth and yield in NH₄NO₃ treatments. Total N uptake in straw was significantly more in azolla treatments; that for grain was higher in the NH₄NO₃ treatments. The percentage uptake of applied N varied from 27-43% in azolla treatments and 30-38% in NH₄NO₃. ☞

Effect of slow-release urea materials on rice yield

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In Tamil Nadu, rice fields are alternately submerged and drained, which encourages nitrification of applied fertilizers and reduces recovery of fertilizer N by 30-40%. We studied the effect of slow-release N fertilizers on TKM9 grain yield in 1984 kharif.

Soil was sandy loam with pH 4.9 and 288-33-112 kg available NPK/ha. The

Effect of slow-release urea materials on growth, yield components, and grain yield of TKM9 at various N levels, Amhasamudram, India.

N level and urea source ^a	Height (cm)	Panicles/hill	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle wt (g)	Filled grains/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over N1 F1	
									N1	F1
N1 F1	81	8.2	19	1.7	70	25.0	5.3	5.6
N1 F2	80	8.8	19	1.8	73	25.6	5.4	5.9	2	2
N1 F3	81	8.7	19	1.8	70	25.4	5.5	6.4	4	4
N1 F4	82	9.2	20	1.9	80	26.2	6.1	6.9	15	15
N2 F1	82	8.6	19	1.7	70	25.2	5.4	5.7	2	2
N2 F2	81	8.6	19	1.7	73	25.4	5.6	6.2	5	5
N2 F3	82	9.2	19	1.7	71	25.5	5.5	6.5	4	4
N2 F4	83	10.0	21	1.9	85	26.2	6.2	1.5	17	17
CD at 5%	1.32	0.87	0.56	0.07	5.88	0.66	0.26	0.99		

^a N levels: N1 = 30 kg, N2 = 75 kg. Urea sources: F1 = prilled urea, F2 = neem cake-coated at 20%, F3 = coal tar-coated at 1%, F4 = USG.

trial was in a split-plot design with three replications. N was applied as neem cake-coated urea at 20%, coal tar-coated urea at 1%, urea supergranules (USG), and prilled urea. When N was split applied, 50% was basal and the rest was in 2 equal splits 15 and 35 d after

transplanting.

Maximum plant height was with 75 kg N/ha as USG, which was at par with 50 kg N as USG. USG and coal tar-coated urea produced maximum panicles per hill and panicle length. USG produced best grain filling and

highest weight followed by neem cake-coated urea (see table).

The interaction of N level and sources significantly influenced grain yield (see table). USG performed best, followed by neem cake-coated urea. *S*

Effect of transplanting schedule and postharvest time intervals for threshing on rice grain yield and head rice recovery

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We evaluated the effect of transplanting schedule and postharvest time intervals for threshing on grain yield and head rice recovery of different rices at the PAU RRS, Kapurthala.

Thirty-five-day-old seedlings of medium-duration Jaya; medium-duration, fine-grained PR106; and short-duration, long-and-slender grained PR103 were transplanted on 1 and 15 Jun (early), 30 Jun, 15 Jul (optimum), or 30 Jul (late). The experiment was in a randomized block design with four replications. At harvest, the main plot was divided into five subplots. The harvested crop was left in the field in small piles for threshing at different times.

1. Effect of transplanting schedule on grain yield of three rices.

2. Effect of transplanting schedule and postharvest time intervals for threshing on head rice recovery (raw and parboiled) of 3 rices.

All varieties yielded highest when planted on 30 Jun (Fig. 1). Yield reduction was most severe when PR 103 (short duration) was transplanted 1 Jun and medium-duration Jaya and PR106 were transplanted 15 and 30 Jul. At optimum transplanting time, varieties had high dry matter production, tiller and spikelet fertility, and 1,000-grain weight.

Labor shortages often require a harvested crop to remain in the field for several days before threshing. The difference in day and night temperature and night dew formation cause cracks and fissures in the grain, and therefore breakage during milling. Threshing within 2 d of harvesting gave significantly higher head yield than delayed threshing (Fig. 2).